

Morphological annotation and translation of Pelliot tibétain 1096¹

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¹ For a translation and text analysis, see Bialek, Joanna. 2021. "The Organization of Stage Stations in Central Asian Colonial Provinces of the Tibetan Empire according to Pelliot tibétain 1096r." *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society* 31 (4):693–709. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1356186321000316>.

(r1) § // *γbrug=gi lo=yi ston sla_ba*
 dragon=GEN year=GEN autumn month

čuñs=gyi ño=la // qan_bcan_zigs_chan=gyi rta gčig // pho_ña
 last=GEN first_half=ALL Qan_bcan_zigs_chan=GEN horse one(ABS) messenger

gžams_(r2)_khoñ_khri γcal=čiñ / par_kog=gi chugsu mčis=nas //
 Gžams_khoñ_khri(ABS) request(NPFV)=DUR Par_kog=GEN encampment:TERM come:PFV=EL

In the first half of the last autumn month of the dragon year, the messenger Gžams-khoñ-khri came to the encampment of Par-kog, asking for one horse of Qan-bcan-zigs-chan.

slar zlogs=payi rigs=pa=las // sluñs=gyi dphon+sna
 back:TERM cause_to_return=NMZ:GEN be_suitable=NMZ=DEL station=GEN head+deputy

(r3) *chugs+phon=la scogs=pa // rta*
 station+head=ALL among_others=NMZ(ABS) horse(ABS)

phrogste // chugsu bžag=pa=las // stor=čhes mčiste //
 (NPFV)rob:GER encampment:TERM PFV:put_in=NMZ=DEL be_lost=QUOT say:GER

Upon it was necessary to send [the horse] back, deputies of the head of the stage station, head of the encampment, among others, said: "Having taken away the horse, [we] placed [it] in the encampment. Thereupon [it] got lost."

rta slar ma (r4) scal=nas // sluñs=gyi
 horse(ABS) back:TERM NEG give.HON(PFV)=EL station=GEN

rta+rji li qab_sab_ñañ / bzuñste rmas=pa=las //
 horse+herdsman Li Qab_sab_ñañ(ABS) (PFV)seize:GER ask:PFV=NMZ=DEL

After [they] had not given the horse back, having seized Li Qab-sab-ñañ, the groom of the stage station, [one] inquired [him].

sluñs+chugsu rta bdag=čhag=(r5)=gis bžag=pa=yañ mad //
 station+encampment:TERM horse(ABS) 1SG=PL=ERG PFV:put_in=NMZ(ABS)=ADD COP.EMPH

li žen_γdo=la gthad=pa=las // rta snar_mo
 Li Žen_γdo=ALL deliver=NMZ=DEL horse light_brown(ABS)

stor=čhes mčiste /
 be_lost=QUOT say:GER

Thereupon [the groom] said: "It is true that we put the horse in the encampment of the stage station. Upon handing [it] over to Li Žen-γdo, the light brown horse got lost."

(r6) *qab_sab_ñañ / žan_γdo=yañ khug=la // rmos=te /*
 Qab_sab_ñañ Žañ_γdo(ABS)=ADD summon:SPASS=ALL speak:PFV=GER

rta γdi chugsu bžag=pa=las/ stor=pa
 horse PROX.DEM(ABS) encampment:TERM PFV:put_in=NMZ=DEL get_lost=NMZ(ABS)

ma lags=(r7)=re// bdag=čhag=gis sbyañs=re brkus=re=śes
 NEG COP=EMPH.NEG 1SG.HML=PL=ERG clear:PFV=EMPH.NEG PFV:steal=EMPH.NEG=QUOT

bro+dkar=gis/ thob{s}=śig/
 oath+white=ERG LV.SPASS=IMP

"Summon Qab-sab-ñañ, as well as Žan-γdo, and, having spoken [to them], swear a sincere oath: 'Upon putting this horse in the encampment, the lost one was indeed there. We have not taken [it] away. [We] have not stolen [it]!'"

bro phod=na skyin_ba phob{s}=śig bro
 oath(ABS) be_able=INESS replacement(ABS) throw:SPASS=IMP oath(ABS)

ma phod=na // khrimś bźin gčhad=par
 NEG be_able=INESS law(ABS) like DPASS:decide=NMZ:TERM

bgyis=te // kho_na qab_sab_ñañ=la (r9) scogs=pa //
 make:PFV=GER 3SG Qab_sab_ñañ=ALL among_others(ABS)

dkar drus /
 sincerity(ABS) examine:PFV

If [you] can make the vow, give a replacement! If [you] cannot make the vow, being decided according to the law, [one] will have examined the sincerity (*dkar*) regarding the very Qab-sab-ñañ, among others.”

lan γdiyī dgun sla ra ba
 year PROX.DEM:GEN winter month first(ABS)

ches brgyad=la bgyis=pa=las / ches bču+bźiyī
 day eight=ALL make:PFV=NMZ=DEL day ten+four:GEN

(r10) *bar=du qab_sab_ñañ=dañ / khuñś_po źan_γdo=yañ*
 middle=TERM Qab_sab_ñañ=COM worker Žan_γdo(ABS)=ADD

ma mčhis=nas // chugs+phon / yo_gaṅ (r11)
 NEG come:PFV=EL encampment+head Yo_gaṅ

g.yu_la_skyes grar bkugste rmas=pa=las //
 G.yu_la_skyes(ABS) court:TERM PFV:summon:GER ask:PFV=NMZ=DEL

Upon having said [so] on the eighth day of the first winter month of this year, up to the fourteenth day [of the month] Qab-sab-ñañ as well as the worker Žan-γdo did not come. Then, having summoned Yo-gaṅ G.yu-la-skyes, the head of the encampment, to the court, [one] inquired [him].

pho_ñā gźams_khoṅ_khri / śa_ču=pa=γī rta gčhig
 messenger Gźams_khoṅ_khri(ABS) Śa_ču=NMZ=GEN horse one(ABS)

(r12) *γcal=te // par_kog=gi chugsu mčhis=pa=las //*
 request=GER Par_kog=GEN encampment:TERM come:PFV=NMZ=DEL

“The messenger Gźams-khoṅ-khri, having asked for one horse of a man from Śa-ču, came to the encampment of Par-kog.

rta γdī pho_ñā=dañ / rta+rjī qab_sab_ñañ
 horse PROX.DEM(ABS) messenger=COM horse+herdsman Qab_sab_ñañ

gñis=gyis rta+/+pho (r13) skyon=bar bgyis=pa=las //
 two=ERG horse+NMZ.M(ABS) mount=NMZ:TERM make:PFV=NMZ=DEL

pho_ñāṅ maṅ+po=ni ma mčhis //
 messenger many+NMZ=FOC NEG EXIST

Thereupon, as for this horse, both the messenger and the groom Qab-sab-ñañ prepared to mount the stallion. There were not many messengers.

pho_ñā rkya γgaγ mčhis=pa=la// śa_ču+pa=γī
 messenger horseman some(ABS) come:PFV=NMZ=ALL Śa_ču+NMZ:GEN

rta bya bsdam=pa=la ma thug=śes//
 horse(ABS) ? DPASS:bind=NMZ=ALL NEG meet=QUOT

pho_ñā=dañ rta+rji=la bdag=gis bgyis//
 messenger=COM horse+keeper=ALL 1SG.HML=ERG make:PFV

After some messenger-horsemen had come and the horse of the man from Śa-ču was bound, I said to the messenger(s) and the groom: ‘[The horses shall] not come across [each other].’

rta ga=la mčis=pa / loñ=la sky{o}l (r15) slar
 horse(ABS) what=ALL exist=NMZ(ABS) catch.SPASS=ALL bring.SPASS back:TERM

skris=śig rta+rji=la=yañ bdag=gis bsgos=pa=las //
 bind:SPASS=IMP horse+herdsman=ALL=ADD 1SG.HML=ERG PFV:order=NMZ=DEL

I ordered to the groom ‘Catch the horses whomever [they] belong to, bring [them], [and] bind [them] again!’

phyi de nañ_par jeyu_hiñ_yir slar
 later DIST.DEM(ABS) day_after_tomorrow(ABS) Jeyu_hiñ_yir back:TERM

chugsu (r16) mčhis=te / ñayi rta
 encampment:TERM come:PFV=GER 1SG:GEN horse(ABS)

ga_re=žes rmas=pa=las //
 where=QUOT ask:PFV=NMZ=DEL

Later, the day after the next day, Jeyu-hiñ-yir, having come again to the encampment, asked ‘Where is my horse?’

qab_sab_ñāñ=gi mčhid=naś / śa_ču=pañi rta gñi+ga
 Qab_sab_ñāñ=GEN speech=EL Śa_ču=NMZ:GEN horse two+NMZ(ABS)

sluñs+phon (r17) g.yul_thog=na mčhis=pa=las / jeyu_hiñ_yir=gis
 station+head(ABS) courtyard=INESS EXIST=NMZ=LAS Jeyu_hiñ_yir=ERG

gčig źon gčig khrid=de bros=śes /
 one(ABS) ride one(ABS) lead=GER flee:PFV=QUOT

qab_[sab]_ñāñ=(r18)=la thos // rta=ni bdagis ma
 Qab_sab_ñāñ=ALL hear horse(ABS)=FOC 1SG.HML:ERG NEG

thoñ=žes mčhiy //
 let_free.SPASS=QUOT say

Qab-sab-ñāñ said: ‘Both horses of the man from Śa-ču were in the courtyard [of] the head of the stage station. Thereupon, Jeyu-hiñ-yir, riding a one [and] leading a one, fled away.’ [I] listened to Qab-sab-ñāñ. Concerning the horse, it was not let free by myself.” [Thus Yo-gañ G.yu-la-skyes] said.

rta+bdag hiñ_ce mčhid_śags/ rnam=gčhig=la bdag=gi rta
 horse+owner Hiñ_ce(ABS) speech+aphorism(ABS) ?=NDEF=ALL 1SG.HML=GEN horse(ABS)

chugs+(r19)+khor=na dguñ gsum mčhis=pa / sluñs=gyi
 encampment+pen=INESS night three(ABS) EXIST=NMZ(ABS) station=GEN

rta gžan=gčhig=kyañ ma mčhis=la / rta
 horse other=NDEF(ABS)=ADD NEG EXIST=ALL horse

ydi chugs+phon=gyis myi mthoñ=(r20)=du=yañ myi
 PROX.DEM(ABS) encampment+head=ERG NEG see=TERM=ADD NEG

ruñ=na / rku[s]=su=yañ glo_ba čhuñ=na // khoñ_ta
 be_suitable=INESS steal.SPASS=TERM=ADD breast be_small=INESS 3(ABS)

gar mčhis=žes rmar gsol=žes mčhi //

what:TERM EXIST=QUOT ask:TERM request.HML=QUOT say

As for the pleadings [of] the horse owner Hiñ-ce, [he] was saying: “Once, my horse was three nights long in the pen; there was no other horse of the stage station. If the head of the encampment must have seen this horse, [I] request [you] to ask: ‘If [he] is despondent about [the horse] being stolen, where is he?’”

de=yi che sluñs=gyi bu+gñer čhags //
DIST.DEM=GEN time(ABS) station=GEN child+help(ABS) appear

(r21) *thum_čhu=ma phyi=la čhagste // ju_čhañ*
?=NMZ(ABS) later=ALL appear:GER Ju_čhañ(ABS)

yan_čhad=dañ / lug_luñ man_čad=du gñer=du mčhi=žes
upward=COM Lug_luñ(ABS) downward=TERM help=TERM say=QUOT

mčhi=nas //
say=EL

At that time a minion of the stage station appeared. *thum čhu ma*, having appeared afterwards, said “[I] am coming from Ju-čhañ to Lug-luñ to help.”

dbyañs=(r22)=te bčhad=pa // hiñ_che=la scogs=paḡi rta
clarify:PFV=GER PFV:decide=NMZ(ABS) Hiñ_che=ALL among_others=NMZ:GEN horse

stor=pa // chugs+phon=la scogs=pa=la / brkusu=yañ dog[s]=śes
be_lost=NMZ(ABS) encampment+head=ALL among_others=NMZ=ALL PFV:steal:TERM=ADD fear=QUOT

(r23) *gsol //*
request.HML

Having clarified [the circumstances], [one] decided: “Concerning the lost horses of Hiñ-che, among others, the head of the encampment, among others, truly feared [its] stealing.” [Thus] it was said.

chugs+phon rmas=pa=las / rta ydi chugsu
encampment+head(ABS) ask:PFV=NMZ=DEL horse PROX.DEM(ABS) encampment:TERM

mčhis=pa=las / bdag=gis rta slar (r24)
come:PFV=NMZ=DEL 1SG.HML=ERG horse(ABS) back:TERM

skri[s]=śig=par rta+rji qab_sab_ñañ=la bsgos /
bing:SPASS=IMP=NMZ:TERM horse+herdsman Qab_sab_ñañ=ALL PFV:order

The head of the encampment, upon being inquired, said, “Upon this horse had come to the encampment, I ordered the groom Qab-sab-ñañ that [he] must (*śig* = IMP) bind the horse again.

rnam=čhig=la rta gñi+ga sluñs+phon=gyi g.yul_thog
?=NDEF=ALL horse two+NMZ(ABS) station+head=GEN courtyard(ABS)

(r25) *mčhis=pa=las // jeyu_[hiñ_yir]=gis gčhig žon*
EXIST=NMZ=DEL Jeyu_hiñ_yir=ERG one(ABS) ride

gčhig khrid=de bro[s]=ste soñ=žes // qab_sab_ñañ=la
one(ABS) lead=GER flee:PFV=GER (PFV)go=QUOT Qab_sab_ñañ=ALL

thos=/(r26)=śes mčhiy /
hear=QUOT say

[Qab-sab-ñañ said:] ‘Once, both horses were in the courtyard of the head of the stage station. Thereupon, Jeyu-hiñ-yir, riding a one [and] leading a one, fled away.’ [I] listened to Qab-sab-ñañ.”

qab_sab_ñañ sñar gñay+dus btab=pa=las=kyañ / dus=su
 Qab_sab_ñañ(ABS) early:TERM guarantor+time(ABS) PFV:LV=NMZ=DEL=ADD time=TERM

ma mčhis / žan_γdo=(r27)=yañ ma mčhis //
 NEG come:PFV Žan_γdo(ABS)=ADD NEG come:PFV

After [one] had previously set a time for Qab-sab-ñañ to [secure] guarantors, [he] did not arrive on time. Neither did Žan-γdo arrive.

rta stor=pa tha_sñad γdogs=śiñ bsgyañ=(r: bskyañ)=du
 horse be_lost(ABS) dispute(ABS) NPFV:bind=DUR PFV:defend=TERM

myi ruñ=gis // chugs+phon=yañ gñay (r28)
 NEG be_suitable=ERG encampment+head(ABS)=ADD guarantor(ABS)

scol=la / qab_sab_ñañ=dañ / žan_γdo khug=la // dgun
 give.HON=ALL Qab_sab_ñañ=COM Žan_γdo(ABS) summon(SPASS)=ALL winter

sla ra+ba ña=la mčhid+śags γchol=čhig=(r29)=par
 month first+NMZ(ABS) full_moon_day=ALL speech+aphorism(ABS) request.HML(SPASS)=IMP=NMZ:TERM

bčade //
 PFV:decide:GER

[Decision:] While initiating (lit. fixing) the dispute [over] the lost horses, it was not feasible to settle (lit. defend) [it]. Therefore, [one] decided that the head of the encampment must provide (lit. give) guarantors, summon Qab-sab-ñañ and Žan-γdo, and plead on the full moon day of the first winter month.

g.yu_la_skyes=gyi gñay=la // qan_hwa_hwa=dañ / den_bun_γde=dañ / čañ_stag_bžer=dañ /
 G.yu_la_skyes=GEN guarantor=ALL Qan_hwa_hwa=COM Den_bun_γde=COM Čañ_stag_bžer=COM

yo_(r30)_gañ reyu_skyes=dañ / gñi_ba lha_mthoñ=dañ / śig_śiñ_śiñ=la
 Yo_gañ Reyu_skyes=COM Gñi_ba Lha_mthoñ=COM Śig_śiñ_śiñ=ALL

scogs=payi gñay+rgya=dañ / khoñ_tayi (r31) sug+rgya=dañ //
 among_others=NMZ:GEN guarantor+seal=COM 3:GEN hand+seal=COM

žañ_lon žal_čhe+payi dpañ+rgyas bthab=pha // (eight red seals)
 aristocrat sentence+NMZ:GEN witness+seal:ERG PFV:LV=NMZ(ABS)

Sealed for the guarantors of [Yo-gañ] G.yu-la-skyes with the guarantor seals of Qan-hwa-hwa, Den-bun-γde, Čañ-stag-bžer, Yo-gañ Reyu-skyes, Gñi-ba Lha-mthoñ, and Śig-śiñ-śiñ, among others, with the personal seal of the person concerned (i.e. Yo-gañ G.yu-la-skyes), and with the witness seal of an aristocrat-judge.